

Current distribution and capability on carbon fibre composite materials, copper foil and fasteners

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S/C: Short Circuit

SCF: Solid Copper Foil

1. ABSTRACT

This article explores (1) how to carry electrical currents on the CFRP structure using non-bolted metallic conductors, (2) the current capability of a fastened junction between an element representing an A/C skin (CFRP+ECF) and a metallic element representing an A/C frame and (3) how the AC is distributed in the presence of fasteners.

For all cases (1)/(2)/(3), tests were carried out; additionally, in case (3) simulations were also performed.

Precisely, in each (1)/(2)/(3) case, following use case were tested:

- (1) Transferring currents in the internal CFRP structure:
 - Use of co-cured and co-bonded copper foil
- (2) Current capability of the junction:
 - Different countersank fastener installation
- (3) Current distribution:
 - A test varying the frequency of the AC from 50 to 5000 Hz was performed

Following relevant magnitudes were recorded in the junctions during the tests:

- Electrical resistance
- Thermal elevation for a permanent injection current
- Thermal elevation for a sudden injection of current
- Current distribution among the fasteners

Furthermore, in case (3), simulations have been performed in order to analyze the behaviour of the current distribution in the bolts. The simulated model represents the fastened junction between the skin (metal or CFRP) and a metallic frame, with a cable running parallel to the skin and perpendicular to the frame. A current is injected in the cable to the metallic frame and extracted through the skin.

2. ACRONYMS AND SYMBOLS

A/C: Aircraft

AC: Alternating Current

BM: Bronze Mesh

CFC: Carbon Fiber Composite (same term as CFRP)

CFRP: Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic

ECF: Expanded Copper Foil

LSfP: Lightning Surface Protection

PEC: Perfect Electric Conductor

3. BACKGROUND

In A/C with extensive use of CFRP, for transferring the fault or power return currents, one possible solution is installing a network of strips.

This network of metallic strips are fixed by fasteners to the CFRP structure as can be seen on Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1 - Example of installation of metallic strips on A/C

Figure 2 - Example of installation of metallic strips on A/C

There are two difficulties associated with this solution:

1. Fasteners for fixing the strips to the structure

To attach the strips to the structure, some fasteners are needed (as in Figure 2) or even fasteners and auxiliary elements to fix the strips to the structure (as in Figure 1). However, these measures add weight and cost without contributing to electrical function. They are even disadvantageous from an electrical point of view, as fastening elements reduce the effective cross-section of the strip and increase the resistance.

2. Fasteners with bonding process for interconnecting the strips

The presence of different structural elements and the location of systems do not allow having a continuous metal strip, so several strips have to be used. To ensure that the network of strips has a low resistance to transmit the electrical currents, the individual strips must be electrically well connected. This bonding process usually involves the cleaning of the area of contact, installing the fasteners and at the end seal the junction in order to avoid corrosion. This process is not automatized, and is very time consuming – therefore, in addition of the extra weight and cost of installing the fasteners, it is needed to add the time-consuming activity of applying a bonding process.

Furthermore, as this solution of joint strips has many bonding points, it is needed to ensure that those bonding points are done correctly by measuring the electrical resistance, another manual, time consuming task.

Therefore, this paper explores alternative solutions to reduce or avoid the problems mentioned above.

4. DESCRIPTION OF THE PROPOSED SOLUTIONS

Depending on the “resources” available, two solutions are explored in this paper.

4.1 Use of the A/C skin

On CFRP A/Cs, usually the skin needs to be protected against the effects of the lightning strike – for that purpose, in the external layer on top of the CFRP a LSfP is installed, for example an ECF or a BM.

Figure 3 – Lightning surface protection: ECF (left), BM (right)

Even if the thickness of the LSfP is usually very thin (typically < 100µm, more than 10 times thinner than a strip), the LSfP covers very large areas, then, a large cross section and a low resistance is expected.

Therefore, the skin of the A/C, composed of CFRP + LSfP, is a good candidate to transfer the current instead of using strips – this solution removes the burden #1 mentioned in the section before

In this first solution, it is studied the transfer of current from a metallic element (simulating an existing metallic structural element in the A/C) to the skin using a standard fastening process, in order to avoid the burden #2 (so no need to do a special bonding process).

A simplified version of this solution is represented in Figure 4 – samples are manufactured following this sketch.

Figure 4 – Simplified version – electrical bonding solution when the skin (CFRP + LSfP) is available

4.2 Internal A/C structure

In areas where there are systems but the A/C skin is not close enough to those systems, another solution is foreseen.

In the areas with CFRP, the transfer of current by means of a solid metallic foil is explored – in this paper, a solid copper foil is used. The continuity between the metallic lug (simulating the connection of a system) and the solid foil is done via a bonding process where the surfaces of the lug and the foil are clean in order to decrease the resistance (see Figure 5).

Figure 5 – electrical bonding solution when the skin (CFRP + LSfP) is available

5. PASS-FAIL CRITERIA AND ELECTRICAL PERFORMANCE

Different requirements apply to the bonding or grounding network in an A/C – these tests are focused on the capability of transferring a defined level of current without degrading the CFRP material.

It is considered that the CFRP may be degraded if the thermal elevation during the current injection tests exceeds 20°C (ΔT

< 20°C) in any point of the sample (the LSfP, the CFRP or the fasteners, all shall be below 20°C). This is a conservative figure, assuming the A/C has to operate in very adverse conditions (e.g., in areas where the temperature of the A/C can be very high)

For the level of current injection to be withstand, following categories are defined:

- **Fault current** test: This current is representative of the expected current associated to a short-circuit event
 - 100A, 150A or 200A in DC are injected during 10 seconds.
- **Permanent current** test: represents the expected current that can be injected as the power return of a system
 - 35A or 55A in DC are injected during 20 minutes.
- **Lightning conducted** tests: represents the expected conducted currents that can flow due to a lightning strike
 - Representative of a lightning zone 2B¹ [1].

For AC the current tends to concentrate around the cable – therefore tests and simulation are done for assessing the effect of the current concentration in AC and how many fasteners are really transferring currents.

6. CURRENT CAPABILITY REPRODUCING INTERNAL STRUCTURE

6.1 Samples description

There are two ways of installing a foil as in Figure 5, by a cocured or a cobonded process.

Cobonded process was discarded due to two main reasons, first it produces a second temperature increment in the CFRP after curing and it could affect the panel structure and secondly it represented an additional manufacturing process, increasing time and cost.

Therefore, it is decided to test the **cocured** solution considering different copper foils options.

A typical strip used for bonding or grounding functions is made of aluminum and have a 20mm² cross-section. For having the SCF the same resistance as the aluminum strips, a cross section of around 12mm² is needed.

Due to external problems related to the supply of this copper foil, at the end only a SCF of 4,2mm² cross-section (thickness=0.070mm and width=60mm) and a SCF of 1,4mm² cross-section (thickness=0.035mm, width=40mm) are used.

Following figure shows the final result of cocuring the SCF on the CFRP

Figure 6 – Cocuring of the SCF on the CFRP

Two samples were manufactured following the principle of the Figure 5, sample S1, where a SCF of 4,2mm² cross section is installed, and sample S2 where a SCF of 1,4mm² cross section is installed.

6.2 Testing

6.2.1 Test set-up

Fault and permanent current tests

The fault and permanent current tests were performed in the same test rig taking into account the currents and times defined in section 5. Specimens were mounted on an isolated structure, clamped mechanically and connected to the generator by copper sheets/braids.

The temperature measurements were made by means of six thermocouples installed on different locations depending on the sample and a thermal camera pointing at the front side of the sample under test.

Figure 7 - Fault and permanent current test rig

Lightning conducted tests

The specimens were mounted on a wooden structure and clamped mechanically. The sample was connected to the current injection point and the current return path by means of copper sheets. The temperature measurement was made by a thermal camera pointing at the front side of the sample under test.

¹ According to ED-84A

Figure 8 - Lightning current test rig

6.2.2 Test results

The location of the six thermocouples in sample S1 and S2 is indicated in the following picture:

Figure 9 - Sample S1&S2 thermocouple location

Note: There is no picture for the backside of the sample, where thermocouple T6 was placed. T6 was positioned in the middle of the sample, in the same location than T3, but on the backside.

Following table summarizes the tests performed in sample S1&S2:

Table 1. Sample S1&S2 test results

Sample	Test		Maximum temperature increment							Thermal Camera	
			Thermocouples							Tmax (°C)	Tmax (°C)
			T1 (°C)	T2 (°C)	T3 (°C)	T4 (°C)	T5 (°C)	T6 (°C)	Tmax (°C)		
S1	Permanent current	35A during 20min	1.5	3.1	3.5	3.4	3.4	3.2	3.5	7.3	
	Fault current	150A during 10s	1.3	3.8	5.1	4.9	4.4	4.7	5.1	7.5	
S2	Permanent current	35A during 20min	6.5	9.8	13.6	1.4	8.1	13	13.6	13	
	Fault current	150A during 10s	9.7	21.4	24.8	24.8	13.1	18.3	24.8	27.1	

Very good results were obtained in all tests for sample S1, with a temperature rise below the limit in all cases, including the thermal camera.

For sample S2, good results were obtained in 35A test, with a temperature rise below the limit in all cases, including the thermal camera. However during 150A test there were temperature increments above the limit (but very close).

These tests showed that a SCF of 4,2mm² cross section can conduct all currents without raising the temperature above the given limit, and a SCF of 1,4mm² cross section is in the limit, with temperature increments close to the requirement of 20°C, see Figure 10.

Figure 10 - Thermal camera on the SCF

7. CURRENT CAPABILITY REPRODUCING THE A/C SKIN

7.1 Sample description

Following the principle of Figure 4, sample S3 was manufactured (see Figure 11); during the test phase, an error regarding the installation of the countersunk fasteners in sample S3 was detected (see Figure 13), therefore a new sample with the right fastening was manufactured, S3' and tested.

7.2 Testing

7.2.1 Test set-up

Same test set-up than previously detailed in 6.2.1-Test set-up.

7.2.2 Test results

The location of the six thermocouples in sample S3 is indicated in the following picture:

Figure 11 - Sample S3 thermocouple's location

Following table summarizes the tests performed in sample S3:

Table 2. Sample S3 test results

Sample	Test		Maximum temperature increment							Thermal Camera Tmax (°C)
			Thermocouples							
			T1 (°C)	T2 (°C)	T3 (°C)	T4 (°C)	T5 (°C)	T6 (°C)	Tmax (°C)	
S3	Permanent current	35A during 20min	9.2	1.5	2.1	7.7	10.5	2.4	12.1	--- (*)
		55A during 20min	4.3	4.5	4.9	5.1	5.5	4.4	5.5	7.1
	Fault current	100A during 10s	0.7	1	1.5	1.3	1.8	1.4	1.8	4.2
		150A during 10s	1.1	1.5	2.6	2.1	2.7	1.9	2.7	8.1
		200A during 10s	2	2.6	4.5	3.4	4.5	3	4.5	13.8

Note: Due to an error, the thermal increment could not be captured by the Thermal Camera in the case highlighted in the table with (*).

Very good results were obtained in all tests on sample S3, with a temperature rise below the limit in all cases, including the thermal camera.

Following table summarizes the tests performed in sample S3':

Table 3. Sample S3' test results

Sample	Test		Maximum temperature increment							Thermal Camera Tmax (°C)
			Thermocouples							
			T1 (°C)	T2 (°C)	T3 (°C)	T4 (°C)	T5 (°C)	T6 (°C)	Tmax (°C)	
S3'	Permanent current	35A during 20min	4.4	10	7.5	8.3	18.6	7.9	18.6	65
	Fault current	150A during 10s	19.1	0.8	3.7	4.8	27.2	2.9	27.2	252.9

Looking at thermocouples results, some temperature increments were above 20°C, but very close to the limit.

Regarding the thermal camera results, the maximum temperature was obtained in the center of the fasteners, as can be seen in Fig. 5. It means that the temperature rise in the CFRP is expected below that value.

Figure 12 - Maximum temperature recorded by thermal camera

Even so, as sample with wrong countersunk (see Figure 13 to see how is the installation of a wrong countersunk) obtained better test results than sample with correct countersunk, micrographs were performed to look for a rationale behind.

Figure 13 - Micrograph on sample with wrong countersunk

It was observed that there was galvanic contact in some areas between the fasteners and the ECF, creating a direct path for conducting all currents without a significant temperature increment.

8. CURRENT DISTRIBUTION - AC PHENOMENA

8.1 Testing

The purpose of this test was to determine whether there was any difference in the current distribution between AC and DC frequencies.

A test varying the frequency of the AC current was performed in order to evaluate if a short-circuit in an AC internal harness in the aircraft could cause a different current distribution on the external side of the structure.

The test was performed on the same sample of section 7. On one side of the panel, the fourteen fasteners were attached to only one metallic plate. On the other side of the panel, a metallic plate was located for each two fasteners, resulting in a total of seven metallic plates. Then, a Shunt resistance was located in series with each metallic plate, in order to measure the current through this Shunt resistance and being able to get the precise current distribution when varying the frequency. All Shunt resistances were calibrated and had the same value.

Fig. 7 shows a general view of the test rig, indicating the position of the wire below the sample for the current return, representing the AC internal harness in the aircraft (under shunt resistance 4).

Figure 14 - Current distribution test set-up

Following table shows the results for the AC current distribution tests. It shows the current distribution in percentage of the total current injected for different frequencies. The proposed test procedure was to sweep from 50 to 5000 Hz and, after that, perform a final check on 50 Hz.

Table 4. AC current distribution

	Shunt 1	Shunt 2	Shunt 3	Shunt 4	Shunt 5	Shunt 6	Shunt 7
50 Hz	20,50%	7,30%	5,37%	21,85%	17,35%	11,40%	16,22%
1600 Hz	19,70%	7,09%	6,39%	22,53%	17,16%	11,29%	15,83%
3200 Hz	18,32%	7,42%	8,31%	22,73%	16,84%	11,04%	15,33%
5000 Hz	16,80%	8,20%	10,47%	23,15%	16,24%	10,47%	14,67%
50 Hz	20,49%	7,30%	5,27%	22,07%	17,28%	11,47%	16,12%

Following table summarizes the partial % increments from 50Hz to 5000Hz.

Table 5. AC current distribution - partial increments

Increment	Shunt 1	Shunt 2	Shunt 3	Shunt 4	Shunt 5	Shunt 6	Shunt 7
50Hz->1600Hz	-0,80%	-0,21%	1,02%	0,68%	-0,19%	-0,11%	-0,39%
1600Hz->3200Hz	-1,38%	0,33%	1,92%	0,20%	-0,33%	-0,25%	-0,50%
3200Hz->5000Hz	-1,52%	0,78%	2,16%	0,41%	-0,60%	-0,57%	-0,66%
50Hz->5000Hz	-3,70%	0,90%	5,10%	1,30%	-1,11%	-0,93%	-1,55%

Figure 15 - AC current distribution - partial increments

It can be shown that most of the % the largest part of the percentage increase is primarily accounted for by Shunt 2, Shunt 3 and Shunt 4, but not with significant values.

In addition to the AC tests, several simulations were performed in order to reproduce this phenomenon. Results of these simulations are detailed in the following paragraph.

8.2 Analysis by simulations

Beforehand, simulations were performed using the Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD) method from the University of Granada (UGR) [2] in order to check the behaviour to be expected. A simple electromagnetic (EM) model can be used to analyse the current distribution in a fastened junction due to a fault current coming from an item of equipment. It is depicted in Fig. 16 and consists of:

- a flat plate 1 m by 1 m representing the fuselage (in brown); configurations with two different materials are analysed: metal using Perfect Electric Conductor (PEC) material, and composite (CFC+ECF) with conductivity of $2.14e5$ S/m (CFRP and ECF anisotropies are not considered in the model since it is not expected they strongly influence the results [3]) and thickness of 3 mm
- a transversal plate 1 m by 0.1 m representing the metallic frame (in grey)
- 19 bolts between both plates evenly spaced every 5 cm with the central bolt in the middle of the plate (in red); they have been modelled either as lumped elements or 1-cell thin wires; configurations with two different resistances are analysed: $1\text{ m}\Omega$ and $15\text{ m}\Omega$
- a cable 5 cm height also centred in the plate and loaded with $5\text{ m}\Omega$ at both ends so as to facilitate the convergence (in blue)
- probes located at every bolt

- probes aligned transversally to the fuselage plate (in green).

Figure 16 - EM model with 19 bolts

With this set-up, the current injected into the cable flows to the metallic frame, then through some of the bolts and finally along the skin. Initially, results at 800 Hz were searched for (double of the power line nominal frequency). A Gaussian pulse with 1 A of amplitude which covers up to 1 MHz with a decay of 6 dB has been used as excitation waveform. Afterwards, a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) was applied to the output files in order to obtain their response in frequency, and they were normalized by the injected current. Finally, values for 800 Hz have been gathered.

Besides, the representativeness of the model was studied by the analysis of several configurations. In this way, it was proved that the 1m by 1 m flat plate could be replaced by a longer one, or a larger one, or being closed surface, without affecting the main conclusions of this study.

Post-processing of simulation results yields graphs of current distribution through bolts and fuselage for the four configurations analysed (PEC- $1\text{ m}\Omega$, PEC- $15\text{ m}\Omega$, CFC+ECF- $1\text{ m}\Omega$ and CFC+ECF- $15\text{ m}\Omega$; see Fig. 17).

Current is distributed among the bolts in a quite uniform way (see red curves). It can be seen that the higher the resistance the more uniform is the current, which is a configuration more representative of a real CFC-metal junction.

Regarding the fuselage probes (see green curves), on a PEC fuselage, the current return is concentrated in a narrow area below the cable in order to reduce the mutual impedance of the current loop. In fact, 90% of the current flows in around 45 cm centred below the cable. On a CFC+ECF fuselage, the current is more spread than in the PEC case, but it is still concentrated in the centre below the cable. In particular, 90% of the current flows in around 75 cm for CFC+ECF.

Figure 17 - Current distribution for different configurations (19 bolts, 800 Hz)

Images of current distribution allow us to visualize the current paths. In Fig. 18, an image with the surface current distribution at 800 Hz is shown (it corresponds to configuration in PEC with 15 mΩ bolts). Red colour, which means high current in the contour plot, can be observed at the bolts (thin wires) and in an area centred below the cable.

Figure 18 - Current distribution image for PEC - 15 mΩ configuration (19 bolts, 800 Hz)

After that, the influence of having more bolts was analysed. Moreover, in this study with a larger flat plate with more bolts, the ‘cut-off frequency’ of the uniform behaviour of the current repartition through the bolts, and the effect of a metallic strip performing the role of a diverter were determined.

The EM model was modified as shown in Fig. 19

- fuselage flat plate of 4 m by 1 m made of composite material (CFC+ECF)
- frame transversal plate of 4 m by 0.1 m
- 79 bolts with a resistance of 15 mΩ.

The same post-process as before was applied, but, in this case, several frequencies are analysed.

Figure 19 - EM model with 79 bolts

Fig. 20 presents the results for this larger model. The main conclusion is that, the higher the frequency, the lower number of bolts carries the current (the higher the frequency, the narrower the corresponding red curve).

Figure 20 - Current distribution for frequencies 800 Hz, 10 kHz, 100 kHz and 1 MHz (79 bolts)

In fact, at a frequency of 800 Hz, the current is spread by tens of bolts, whereas it is less spread along the fuselage. Higher frequencies have been analysed in order to estimate the frequency limit at which the current distribution in the bolts is no longer uniform but it is concentrated in a narrow area below the cable in order to reduce the mutual impedance of the current loop. Thus, for 10 kHz, current is distributed by approximately half the bolts, but a narrower fuselage area, so that the repartition through the bolts is still observed. At 100 kHz, the current is distributed by the same number of bolts than probes in the fuselage. Consequently, at 1 MHz, definitely the current is concentrated below the cable either through the fuselage or through the bolts.

Note that, although the conclusions remain the same, the lower number of bolts the more uniform repartition is produced, that is, the uniformity observed in a sample with less bolts (Fig. 16) is more pronounced than the one obtained for a sample with more bolts (see Fig. 19).

Table 6 analyses the current distribution as a function of the frequency. It consists of five columns, the frequency, the number of probes placed at the bolts through which passes at least 90% of the current, the accurate percentage of current flowing through the probes in the previous column, the number of probes aligned transversally to the fuselage plate (depicted in green in Fig. 19) through which passes at least 90% of the current, and the accurate percentage of current flowing through the probes in the previous column. It reveals that the 'cut-off' frequency at which the current is no longer more spread through the bolts than through the fuselage probes is around 50 kHz.

Table 6. Bolt and Fuselage Probes through which passes at least 90% of the current

Frequency	Bolts		Fuselage	
	Number of Probes	Percentage of Current	Number of Probes	Percentage of Current
DC	45	90	33	91
10 kHz	17	94	9	91
20 kHz	13	94	9	90
30 kHz	11	93	11	92
40 kHz	11	96	11	92
50 kHz	9	91	11	92
60 kHz - 1 MHz	9	91 - 94	11	90 - 91

Finally, the effect of a metallic strip in the fuselage plate at a distance from the centred cable was analysed. The results for three positions of the strip are shown in Fig. 21 (between 32 and 33 bolts, 20 and 21 bolts, and 10 and 11 bolts) for a

frequency of 800 Hz. The closer to the cable the diverter is, and the lower the frequency, the more current flows along the diverter. However, current flowing through the central bolt is not significantly reduced, and, therefore, diverter solution does not seem the proper one here.

Figure 21 - Diverter analysis

8.3 Conclusions on AC current distribution

Fig. 22 shows:

- The measured increase of current when increasing from 50Hz to 1600Hz (black line)
- The simulated increase of current when increasing from 50Hz to 1600Hz (orange line)

Since the current measurement with the Shunt is made for each 2 fasteners, the simulation has been grouped in the same way. However, the simulation sample has an odd number of fasteners while the measured sample has an even number of fasteners, so there will be an imbalance when grouping the bolts. On the other hand, the size of the samples and the bolt resistances are not the same. Therefore, the comparison is not intended to validate results, but to compare order of magnitudes and trends.

Indeed, as can be seen in Fig. 22, the order of magnitude is very similar, and the trends are also similar: increase of current in the area surrounding the cable, and decrease in the fasteners further from the cable.

Figure 22 - Order of magnitude and trend comparison between measurement and simulation

9. CONCLUSIONS

It has been analyzed, for the currents specified on section 5, taking into account the degradation of the CFRP (as $\Delta T < 20^\circ\text{C}$), the current capability of:

- a) A **solid copper foil** cured on top of the CFRP

When the cross section is 4,2mm² the thermal elevation is considered acceptable with some margin. With the smaller cross section 1,4mm², it is just in the very limit of the thermal elevation requirement.

- b) A metallic element connected to the skin (CFRP + ECF) of the A/C through **fasteners** without any specific bonding process

With the “wrong” countersunk fastener installation, the thermal elevation criteria is pass with margin, whilst with the “right” countersunk installation, the requirement is NOT passed.

Also it is studied the

- c) **Distribution of current** as a function of the frequency

Simulation shows that up to around 50 kHz the current is quite distributed among the fasteners, up from that value, current start to be very concentrated in the fasteners closer to the cable.

Also tests for measuring the influence of the current distribution were carried out, and the same trend and same order of magnitude as in the simulations is achieved.

10. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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